

Biobased composite fibers and films with keratin from chicken feathers as matrix and calcium carbonate as nanoreinforcement materials

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Problems with petro-based fibers and composites

- Sustainability
- Environmental and health problems
 - Particles found in rainfall and in snow
 - Accumulated in human body
- Alternatives
 - Sustainable
 - Responsible
 - Profitable

Keratinous wastes

- Safe and abundant
 - At least 5 millions tons of chicken feather/year globally
 - 2.5 times higher than the current annual production of both wool and silk
 - Protein content: > 90%
- Good property
 - High degrees of crosslinkages
 - Good tensile property
 - Good water stability

Preparation of keratin fiber and keratin films

Morphological structure of films and fibers

- Keratin films
 - Thickness: around 0.12 mm
- Fine fibers produced
 - 15-20 μm in diameter
- Good recovery of crystallinity
 - Fine alignment of molecules
- High concentration of beta-sheet
 - High drawing ratio

Materials	Degree of crystallinity		
	Total crystallinity	Portion of α -helix	Portion of β -sheet
Chicken feather	31%	11%	20%
Regenerated fibers	24%	5%	19%

Problems of keratinous materials and solutions

- Problems
 - Poor mechanical properties and wet stability
- Solution
 - Reinforcement
- Concerns
 - Compatibility between matrix and reinforcement
 - Decreased strain
- Approach
 - CaCO₃ nanoparticles with excellent compatibility via coordination
 - No plasticizers, therefore, good wet stability

Interactions between CaCO_3 nanoparticles and keratin matrix

Mechanical properties and SEM of CaCO₃/keratin composites

Property improvements for keratin/CaCO₃ films

Keratin resources	Reinforcement	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Breaking Elongation	Ref
Wool	Chitosan	34±10	7±2%	a
Duck feather	cysteine particles	47-68 6 (wet)	4-5% 30% (wet)	b
Chicken feather	chitin nanoparticles	20–35	20–40%	c
Chicken feather	Nanoclay	~4.1	16.5%	d
Chicken feather	CaCO₃ nanoparticle	66-87 3.6-6.1(wet)	10-11% 82-99% (wet)	This work

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Property improvements for keratin/CaCO₃ fibers

	Dry properties		Wet properties		ref
Fiber source	Tensile strength/MPa	Elongation at break/%	Tensile strength/MPa	Elongation at break/%	
Chicken feathers	140-180	6-12	100-140	15-21	1
Wool	120-174	25-35	120-160	42-50	2
Keratin fibers	138±30.5	11±2.8	50-90	25-35	3
Keratin fibers crosslinked with sugar-aldehydes	205±10.5	19±4	120-140	27-35	4
Keratin fibers reinforced with chitin NP	240-260	17-22	150-170	33-38	5
Keratin fibers reinforced with CaCO ₃ NP	208±13	15±2	132±9	60±9	This work

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3. Green Chem., 22 (5) (2020), pp. 1726-1734
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Summary

- Keratinous fibers and films successfully reinforced by CaCO₃ nanoparticles
- Improved tensile strength, elongation and wet stability without plasticizers
- Better than other protein materials
- Potential for textile, agricultural and packaging applications

